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Pathways

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Abbreviations list

API	Application Programming Interface
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution
DCS	DMP Common Standard
DMP	Data Management Plan
DSW	Data Stewardship Wizard
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FTR	FAIR Testing Results
FWF	Fonds zur Förderung der wissenschaftlichen Forschung (German for: Austrian Science Fund)
RDA	Research Data Alliance
SE	Science Europe

Executive Summary

This deliverable (D3.2), **presents the practical implementation of the OSTrails DMP evaluation effort**. Building on [D3.1 \(evaluation framework and service requirements\)](#) and [D4.2 \(dimension validation and Horizon Europe pilot evidence\)](#), it delivers **a) a community-developed metrics catalogue, b) an automated evaluation service, and c) integrations with major DMP platforms**.

The evaluation criteria were developed through a structured community co-design process with data stewards, tool developers, funder representatives, and domain researchers spanning across the 24 pilot communities. The process generated 118 pieces of structured feedback, which directly shaped the prioritisation and formalisation of the metrics.

The resulting OSTrails DMP Evaluation Metrics Catalogue comprises 94 metrics, publicly available as part of OSTrails Commons, formalised as linked-data records using the FTR vocabulary and aligned with the RDA DCS. The catalogue is operationalised through the OSTrails DMP Evaluation Service, which returns machine-readable, field-level evaluation reports and already integrates with [ARGOS](#) and [Data Stewardship Wizard](#), with [DAMAP](#) integration underway.

Specifically, this deliverable contributes:

1. **A formalised DMP Evaluation Metrics Catalogue** comprising 94 linked-data metrics aligned with the [RDA DMP Common Standard](#).
2. **An interoperable evaluation service** supporting deterministic and externally validated checks.
3. **Reusable benchmark profiles** supporting funder, institutional, and thematic evaluation contexts.
4. **Integration of evaluation workflows into operational DMP authoring environments** including ARGOS and Data Stewardship Wizard.
5. **FTR-based machine-readable evaluation outputs** enabling interoperability across OSTrails infrastructures and EOSC-aligned services.

Identified gaps and observations from the co-design process are documented in [Section 3](#) and will inform the next iteration of the catalogue. Planned next steps include additional community benchmarks, extended test coverage, and domain-specific metric layers, coordinated with parallel OSTrails FAIR assessment work.

1. Introduction

This deliverable (D3.2) presents the **practical implementation of the OSTrails DMP evaluation effort**, building on the foundations established in the project's first reporting period. [D3.1](#) defined the evaluation framework, quality dimensions, and service requirements for automated maDMP assessment. [D4.2](#) validated those dimensions through structured stakeholder engagement and documented evidence from 24 Horizon Europe pilots. D3.2 operationalises both: it delivers the community-developed metrics catalogue, the executable evaluation tests, the evaluation service, and the integrations with DMP authoring tools that together constitute the *OSTrails DMP evaluation infrastructure*.

This deliverable is addressed to researchers, data stewards, funders, and tool developers who wish to understand how the OSTrails evaluation framework has been implemented, what metrics are available, how the service works, and how it can be adopted or extended in their own context.

The DMP Evaluation Service is a reference implementation of the OSTrails evaluation framework, available as an open-source tool at <https://github.com/OSTrails/DMP-Evaluation-Service>. It demonstrates how automated evaluation of machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs) conforming to the DMP Common Standard can be operationalised in practice. Evaluation is organised across six dimensions — Content Completeness, Research Data Management Coverage, Openness, FAIRness, Policy Alignment, and Standards Compliance — each operationalised through a set of discrete, executable tests drawn from the metrics catalogue. Built on a Spring Boot/Kotlin backend with MongoDB persistence and a documented REST API, it is designed to be deployed independently or integrated into existing maDMP authoring and review workflows, and to serve as a basis for adoption and extension by the wider community.

The remainder of the deliverable is structured as follows: [Section 2](#) describes the co-design methodology through which evaluation criteria were elicited and prioritised. [Section 3](#) presents the DMP Evaluation Metrics Catalogue. [Section 4](#) documents the DMP

Evaluation Service. [Section 5](#) describes the primary use scenarios supported by the service. [Section 6](#) summarises the contributions and outlines next steps.

2. Methodology

This section describes the approach used to develop the DMP Evaluation Metrics Catalogue. The methodology combined participatory co-design with progressive formalisation, ensuring that the resulting evaluation criteria are grounded in real-world DMP practice, aligned with established standards, and implementable as automated tests.

The catalogue was developed through a structured community co-design process extending and refining the initial evaluation framework established in D3.1 [13]. The methodology comprised three sequential phases: community ideation through a structured workshop, consolidation and prioritisation of candidate checks, and formalisation of retained checks as metric records. The process was further informed by evidence from the Horizon Europe pilot activities documented in D4.2 [4], which identified recurring quality gaps across 24 national pilots that directly shaped the prioritisation of evaluation criteria.

The central activity was a collaborative workshop engaging stakeholders from the OSTrails consortium and pilot ecosystem, including data stewards, tool developers, funder representatives, and domain researchers. The workshop used a shared digital whiteboard, provided by the [Miro tool](#), structured around the six thematic sections of the Science Europe DMP template [17] as organisational anchors. For each section, participants identified specific questions a DMP evaluation system should address, articulated what a check would examine, and assigned a priority score reflecting the perceived importance and implementability of each check.

5 DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

- 5a** How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?
- 5b** How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term (for example a data repository or archive)?
- 5c** What methods or software tools are needed to access and use data?
- 5d** How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier (such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI)) to each data set be ensured?

Figure 1. Example of workshop contributions for Section 5

Checks were defined at two distinct evaluation stages:

- **planning**, where the DMP expresses stated intentions, and
 - **execution**, where those intentions can be validated against observable evidence.
- This dual-stage framing directly shaped the design of the catalogue, as described in [Section 3](#). The workshop generated 118 pieces of structured feedback.

Following the workshop, candidate checks underwent a consolidation and prioritisation process before being formalised as metric records. Inclusion criteria, formalisation details, and the structure of the resulting metric records are described in [Section 3](#).

3. DMP Evaluation Metrics

The OSTrails DMP [Evaluation Metrics Catalogue](#) is publicly available as part of [OSTrails Commons](#) and currently comprises 94 metrics. The catalogue covers all six thematic DMP sections of the Science Europe DMP template and an additional transversal section addressing machine-actionability and DCS schema compliance. The distribution of metrics across quality dimensions and DMP sections reflects the community-stated priorities captured through the workshop priority scores, while ensuring a minimum level of coverage across all sections.

Each metric record contains the following elements: a persistent URI identifier consistent with the identifier patterns established in the OSTrails Reference Architecture [9]; a human-readable name and description; a quality dimension (one of the five defined below); the applicable RDA DCS schema fields [7, 8] and/or OSTrails Application Profile fields ([OSTrails Application Profile for maDMPs - OSTrails Documentation](#)); and the identifiers of the implementing tests.

The five quality dimensions adopted in this catalogue consolidate and refine the seven dimensions introduced in D3.1 [13], by merging openness into FAIRness and adequacy into quality, yielding a more parsimonious and mutually exclusive classification:

- **Completeness:** required fields are present and non-empty.
- **FAIRness:** data and metadata satisfy FAIR criteria.
- **Funder/policy compliance:** requirements of a specific benchmark or funder template are met.
- **Quality:** values are meaningful and well-formed (e.g. a licence field contains a recognised SPDX identifier [3]).
- **Consistency:** values within a DMP are mutually coherent (e.g. an embargo end date falls after the project start date).

Each metric is also assigned a scope classification that determines what sources of evidence it draws upon, mapping directly onto the dual-stage evaluation framing described in [Section 2](#).

Internal-scope metrics operate exclusively on the maDMP document, checking whether declared values are present, non-empty, and formally correct. They require no network access, are fast and deterministic, and apply primarily to the planning stage of the DMP lifecycle. Key examples include verifying that every dataset entry carries a `data_access` field, or that any `distribution.license.license_ref` corresponds to a recognised SPDX identifier [3].

External-scope metrics consult live external sources to extend the evaluation beyond the document. They fall into two sub-types. Feasibility checks verify that stated information is consistent with observable reality: for example, that a declared DOI resolves to a live record, that a repository API returns the referenced dataset, or that the access rights recorded in a repository match those declared in the DMP. Compliance checks verify that declared values meet applicable normative requirements: for example, that the licence declared for a Horizon Europe-funded dataset corresponds to the CC-BY requirement, or that a listed organisation appears as a valid entry in the Research Organisation Registry [14]. These external checks build on the integration model described by Papadopoulou et al. [12], which demonstrated that maDMP field values, including dataset identifiers, repository references, and contributor PIDs, can be systematically cross-referenced against live graph records. Together, the internal and external scope classification extends the quality dimension framework proposed by Arnhold et al. [2] and the initial dimensions introduced in D3.1 [13].

Following the consolidation and prioritisation process described in [Section 2](#), each retained check was formalised as a metric record. Four criteria governed inclusion in the current release:

- **Implementability:** the check can be operationalised as a deterministic binary or three-valued test (pass, fail, or indeterminate).
- **Grounding in the RDA DCS schema:** the check operates on one or more identifiable fields in the RDA DMP Common Standard [7, 8] or the OSTrails Application Profile extension. Checks that could not be mapped to a concrete DCS field were deferred pending schema extension proposals or retained in the candidate backlog pending community agreement.

- **Funder and policy relevance:** the check corresponds to requirements reflected in workshop priority scores and Horizon Europe pilot findings documented in D4.2 [4]. Where priority scores varied substantially across participant groups, this variation was recorded and used to inform the benchmark design described in [Section 4](#).
- **Non-redundancy:** where checks addressed the same concern across different fields, such as PID checks for datasets versus PID checks for contributors, they were retained as separate metrics to preserve precision and independence. Domain-specific extensions identified during the workshop and in D3.4 [16] were retained in a dedicated extension layer to preserve the generality of the core catalogue.

According to the OSTrails FAIR Reference Model, evaluation is organised across three levels: a **benchmark** is a community-specific grouping of metrics that articulates how a particular community defines DMP quality for assessment purposes; a **metric** is a human-readable quality criterion drawn from the catalogue; and a **test** is the software implementation that evaluates a maDMP against a metric criterion and returns pass, fail, or indeterminate. This **benchmark→metric→test hierarchy** governs both the catalogue structure and the service's data model, as described in [Section 4](#). One metric can be covered by multiple tests tailored to different contexts. Persistent identifier checking, for example, is implemented separately for DOI, Handle, ARK, and URL schemes. Test result sets are serialised as JSON-LD following the FTR vocabulary [11], enabling evaluation outcomes to be published as linked data and exchanged across platforms and EOSC-aligned services without loss of provenance.

As a worked example, consider the metric "All datasets described in the DMP carry a persistent identifier." This metric belongs to the FAIRness quality dimension. It has internal scope when checking for the presence of a PID field, and external scope when verifying that the declared PID resolves. The applicable DCS field is `dataset[*].dataset_id.identifier`. The corresponding test verifies that each dataset block carries a non-empty identifier of a recognised PID scheme (DOI, Handle, ARK, ORCID, or URL). The resulting FTR record documents the outcome, a plain-language

explanation, and the full provenance chain, including the subject DMP, the test and metric identifiers, the generating software agent, and a timestamp. The outcome is directly machine-readable and can be surfaced to researchers and data stewards as a pass/fail indicator within DMP authoring tools.

The following observations and gaps were identified during the co-design process and will inform the next iteration of the catalogue:

- **Lifecycle cross-referencing:** some checks in the final DMP are relevant to multiple sections. Initial DMP checks should explicitly address what researchers are planning, with corresponding checks at the final DMP stage to verify whether those plans were implemented.
- **DMP status field:** a status field is needed to enable cross-referencing between an initial and a final DMP, allowing the service to apply the appropriate set of metrics based on the lifecycle stage.
- **Preservation intent flag:** the current DCS includes a `preservation_statement` field but lacks a simple binary field (yes/no) to indicate whether long-term preservation is intended.
- **Recommended formats for long-term preservation:** a controlled list of recommended file formats is needed to enable automated matching against declared formats in the DMP.
- **Access rights vocabulary:** the values open, embargoed, restricted, and closed should map to open, shared, and closed. Additionally, `access_right_embargoed` should be linked to `license_startdate` to support embargo period validation.
- **Controlled vocabulary for cost titles and types:** currently missing and needed to enable automated compliance checking for budget-related DMP sections.
- **Compliance benchmark currency:** it should be verified and documented whether the maDMP compliance benchmark reflects the latest additions to the DCS.
- **Methodology entity:** currently missing from the catalogue scope, limiting the ability to evaluate how research methods are documented in the DMP.

- **Folder structure and data naming conventions:** not currently included and should be added in a future release.
- **Registry coverage:** the current external checks do not fully exploit available registry information. Access rights and file format fields are also missing from the current external validation scope.
- **Quality methods:** checks related to data quality methods are currently absent and should be addressed in the next iteration.

Of the above, four gaps were identified as carrying the highest community priority for the next catalogue iteration: lifecycle cross-referencing, controlled vocabularies for access rights and cost types, extended registry coverage, and checks for quality methods and data naming conventions.

4. The DMP Evaluation Service

The OSTrails DMP Evaluation Service is implemented as a Spring Boot 3 microservice with reactive WebFlux support, designed to evaluate machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs) against the benchmark→metric→test model described in [Section 3](#). The service accepts a maDMP in JSON format compliant with the RDA DMP Common Standard and returns evaluation results serialised as JSON-LD following the FTR vocabulary.

All documentation and the code of the service is available on the OSTrails GitHub repo: <https://github.com/OSTrails/DMP-Evaluation-Service>

4.1. System Architecture

The service follows a layered architecture organised around three core responsibilities: **orchestration**, **plugin-based execution**, and **persistence**.

When a client submits a maDMP file and a benchmark identifier to the `/assess/benchmark` endpoint, the request flow proceeds as follows:

1. EvaluationController receives the multipart request containing the maDMP file and benchmark ID, delegating to the orchestration layer.
2. EvaluationManagerService (orchestration layer) creates an EvaluationReport record, resolves which tests to execute by traversing the benchmark→metric→test chain stored in MongoDB, and dispatches each test to the evaluation layer.
3. EvaluationService (execution layer) retrieves the correct EvaluatorPlugin from the PluginRegistry using the pluginId stored in the TestRecord, then invokes the corresponding function from the plugin's functionMap.
4. EvaluatorPlugin implementations execute the evaluation logic against the maDMP. Currently available plugins cover completeness checks (CompletenessEvaluator, DCSCCompletenessEvaluator), compliance validation (ComplianceEvaluator), feasibility assessment (FeasibilityEvaluator), FAIRness

evaluation via external delegation (FAIRChampionEvaluator), and action quality assessment (QualityOfActionsEvaluator).

- MongoDB persistence layer stores BenchmarkRecords, MetricRecords, TestRecords, and individual Evaluation results, linked via reportId for full traceability.

Figure 2. DMP-Evaluation Service Architecture

Plugin System

The plugin mechanism is the primary extensibility point of the service. Each EvaluatorPlugin implements a standardised interface exposing a functionMap that maps test function names to their implementations. Spring's plugin registry (@EnablePluginRegistries) enables runtime discovery and invocation of plugins without modifying the core service.

Adding a new evaluator requires only three steps:

1. create a class implementing `EvaluatorPlugin` and annotate it with `@Component`
2. Implement `getPluginIdentifier()` returning a unique string
3. Populate `functionMap` with entries mapping function names to their evaluation logic.

Corresponding `TestRecord` entries in MongoDB then reference the `pluginId` and function name. This design decouples evaluation logic from the core execution engine, allowing new evaluation methods to be integrated independently.

External integrations extend the capabilities of certain plugins. All FAIR assessment tools in OSTrails, i.e. [FAIR Champion Test-runner](#), [OpenAIRE FAIR Metadata Validator](#), [FAIROS](#), [FOOPs!](#) delegate FAIR-related tests following the OSTrails FAIR Interoperability Framework API. The OpenAIRE Graph integration enables feasibility checks on open-access status of publications. RML mappers support conversion of maDMP JSON to RDF for semantic validation.

Data Model and Persistence

The data model reflects the benchmark→metric→test hierarchy described in [Section 3](#). `BenchmarkRecords` reference a list of `metricIds`; `MetricRecords` reference a list of `testIds`; `TestRecords` store `pluginId` and `functionName` fields that bind them to executable implementations. `EvaluationReports` are created once per benchmark run and linked to individual Evaluation results via `reportId`.

MongoDB's document-oriented storage provides schema flexibility to support heterogeneous test results, where different evaluators may return different result structures while all conforming to a common result envelope (result status, explanation, affected DMP fields, timestamp, and provenance). Result status uses the standard `ResultTestEnum`: pass, fail, indeterminate.

Deployment

The service is deployed as a containerised Spring Boot application. A Docker Compose configuration is provided to launch both the service and MongoDB. The service requires

Java 17 or higher, MongoDB 6.0 or later, and Maven 3.8+ for local builds. Configuration is managed via `application.yml` and environment variables, including endpoints for external services (FAIR Champion, Unpaywall) and base URLs for benchmark, metric, and test endpoint resolution.

The service exposes its full API via REST endpoints documented in the integrated Swagger UI (available at `/swagger-ui.html` when the service is running). Assessment endpoints (`/assess/benchmark`, `/assess/test`) accept multipart requests and return evaluation results in JSON or JSON-LD format. Management endpoints (`/benchmarks`, `/metrics`, `/tests`, `/plugins`) enable creation, retrieval, and modification of evaluation configurations.

4.2. Evaluation Engine and Test Coverage

The catalogue is implemented in the OSTrails DMP Evaluation Service, a RESTful API publicly available at [https://ostrails-dmp-evaluation.arisnet.ac.at/swagger-ui/index.html#/.](https://ostrails-dmp-evaluation.arisnet.ac.at/swagger-ui/index.html#/)

The service accepts a maDMP JSON document and a benchmark identifier at `POST /assess` and returns an FTR-compliant evaluation report. Test logic is encapsulated in a plugin mechanism: each plugin exports functions implementing one or more catalogue tests, covering completeness, FAIRness, funder compliance, and external validation (PID resolution; RE3data and ROR registry queries). New plugins can be registered without modifying the core engine. Two DMP platforms, i.e. ARGOS and Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW), consume the service API to surface real-time evaluation feedback within their authoring interfaces, following the same loose-coupling pattern: serialise the current DMP as maDMP JSON, submit to `POST /assess` with a benchmark identifier, display the returned report.

Evaluation of Sample DMPs

To demonstrate the end-to-end pipeline, we evaluate two synthetic maDMPs against a benchmark derived from the Science Europe (SE) Practical Guide to Research Data Management. The selected metrics — PID resolvability, open licence compliance, and repository registration — are representative of the quality criteria commonly required

across funder, institutional, and research infrastructure contexts that the project represents and supports. This example is intended to be illustrative: the service's architecture allows any community to define and apply their own benchmark by combining metrics and tests from the catalogue according to their specific requirements.

DMP-A describes a climate observation dataset that violates all three SE requirements: it lacks a persistent identifier, applies a proprietary licence, and designates a repository that is not listed in re3data.

DMP-B describes a biodiversity survey dataset with a declared DOI, a CC BY 4.0 licence, and Zenodo as the target repository. The licence and repository are compliant with SE requirements; however, the DOI does not yet resolve (HTTP 404), which is a common situation when a DMP is authored prior to data deposition.

Both plans conform to the RDA DMP Common Standards (DCS) schema.

```
{
  "dataset": [
    {
      "title": "Climate Observation Dataset",
      "distribution": [{
        "license": [{
          "license_ref": "https://example.com/custom-license"
        }],
        "host": { "url": "https://internal-repo.uni.org" }
      }]
    }
  ]
}
```

Listing 1. DMP-A—no PID, proprietary licence, unregistered repository.

```
{
  "dataset": [
    {
      "dataset_id": {
        "identifier": "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1234567",
        "type": "doi"
      },
      "distribution": [{
        "license": [{
          "license_ref": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/"
        }],
        "host": { "url": "https://zenodo.org" }
      }]
    }
  ]
}
```

Table 1 summarises test outcomes for both DMPs against the three SE metrics. **Figure 3** and **Figure 4** show the corresponding service web interface result.

Table 1. SE benchmark results for two synthetic maDMPs.

Metric	DMP-A	DMP-B
Dataset PID Resolvability	FAIL — missing or invalid identifier	FAIL — DOI resolves to HTTP 404
Open Licence Compliance	FAIL — proprietary licence not in OKF list	PASS — CC BY 4.0 recognised
RE3data Repository Registration	FAIL — not found in RE3data	PASS — Zenodo (r3d100010468)

The results illustrate three properties of the catalogue in practice. First, external checks are dynamically validated: the licence check queries the Open Knowledge Foundation Licenses registry, and the repository check queries RE3data at runtime, so results always reflect the current state of external registries. Second, failure explanations are actionable at field level each result identifies the specific DCS field responsible, enabling targeted revision. Third, DMP-B's partial compliance profile demonstrates that the catalogue correctly disaggregates results by metric, giving researchers a precise view of which requirements they satisfy, and which remain open, a more actionable signal than a single aggregate score.

Dataset Persistent Identifier Check

FAIL

Checks that each dataset in the maDMP has a valid persistent identifier type (doi, handle, ark, url, other) and that the identifier is resolvable via HTTP GET. The test fails if any dataset has a missing, invalid, or unresolvable identifier.

🔍
Details
>

Dataset Open License Check

FAIL

Checks that every distribution of every dataset in the maDMP is assigned a recognized open license, verified against the Open Knowledge Foundation Open Definition license list. Fails if any distribution is missing a license or has a non-open license.

🔍
Details
>

Dataset Repository is Registered in RE3data

FAIL

Checks whether the repository declared in each dataset distribution (dmp.dataset[*].distribution[*].host.url) is registered in the RE3data global registry of research data repositories (re3data.org). The host URL is normalized to its domain, queried through the RE3data OpenSearch suggest endpoint to retrieve candidate repository names, matched

Figure 3. DMP-A evaluation: all three tests fail with field-level explanations.

Dataset Persistent Identifier Check FAIL

Checks that each dataset in the maDMP has a valid persistent identifier type (doi, handle, ark, url, other) and that the identifier is resolvable via HTTP GET. The test fails if any dataset has a missing, invalid, or unresolvable identifier.

[Details](#)

Dataset Open License Check PASS

Checks that every distribution of every dataset in the maDMP is assigned a recognized open license, verified against the Open Knowledge Foundation Open Definition license list. Fails if any distribution is missing a license or has a non-open license.

[Details](#)

Dataset Repository is Registered in RE3data PASS

Checks whether the repository declared in each dataset distribution (dmp.dataset[*].distribution[*].host.url) is registered in the RE3data global registry of research data repositories (re3data.org). The host URL is normalized to its domain, queried through the RE3data OpenSearch

Figure 4. DMP-B evaluation: PID resolvability fails; licence and repository tests pass.

The complete source code for the OSTrails DMP Evaluation Service is publicly available on GitHub: <https://github.com/OSTrails/DMP-Evaluation-Service>. The repository contains the full implementation in Kotlin using Spring Boot 3, and comprehensive documentation for deployment and extension.

Figure 5. GitHub DMP Evaluation Service

4.3. Tool Integrations

Three DMP authoring tools, ARGOS, DAMAP, and Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW), already consume the service API to provide real-time evaluation feedback within their authoring interfaces.

The integration pattern is consistent: the current DMP is serialised as maDMP JSON, submitted to the evaluation endpoint with a benchmark identifier, and the returned report is displayed to the user.

4.3.1. ARGOS

In ARGOS, the DMP evaluation is available via plugin extension, accessible from the DMP overview tab alongside the DMP's metadata and content. The same plugin is available in [OpenCDMP](#), the open-source platform underlying ARGOS.

Users can select from the full list of available metrics and benchmarks and apply their chosen combination directly to their DMP, giving them granular control over the evaluation scope rather than a fixed benchmark. **Figure 6** illustrates the evaluation selection interface within the ARGOS DMP overview tab.

Figure 6. Evaluation selection in ARGOS

The service returns field-level pass/fail results with targeted guidance on what specifically failed and how it can be addressed, as shown in **Figure 7**.

Figure 7. Passed/Failed results of the DMP Evaluator in ARGOS

Evaluation records are persisted and remain accessible from the user's DMP dashboard, allowing researchers and data stewards to track compliance over time and across DMP versions. **Figure 8** shows the validation history view accessible from the dashboard.

Figure 8. Archived results of the DMP Evaluator in ARGOS

4.3.2. DAMAP

The DMP Evaluation feature has been integrated into the overview section of each individual DMP within DAMAP. Alongside the existing overview displaying the completion status of each DMP section, users can now evaluate their DMP against a benchmark of their choice. The primary use case is evaluation against the baseline FWF requirements — a benchmark particularly relevant for the Austrian research community.

Figure 9 illustrates the updated DAMAP user interface reflecting this new functionality. **Figure 10** presents the results of a benchmark run. The results are indicative in nature, meaning users retain full ability to modify and extend the generated document. Importantly, the evaluation operates on the machine-actionable DMP (maDMP) and is independent of the export format used for a traditional DMP.

Figure 9. DAMAP user interface with the integrated DMP Evaluation section.

4.3.3. DSW and FAIR Wizard

In DSW and FAIR Wizard, the DMP Evaluation feature is available via plugin extension in the project tab. It allows users to run Tests and Benchmarks on their filled DMP (Project). The extension is configurable, so it can be connected to any existing DMP Evaluation service that is compliant with the OSTrails reference DMP Evaluation Service.

Figure 11 showcases the selection of the benchmark for evaluating the DMP (Project) in FAIR Wizard.

Figure 12 and Figure 13 present the results of a benchmark run. They show both passed and failed tests, together with all relevant information and metadata, providing researchers with clear feedback on the results.

Figure 11. FAIR Wizard project tab with the evaluation selection.

The screenshot shows the FAIR Wizard interface for an 'Example project'. The left sidebar contains navigation options: Dashboard, Knowledge Models, Document Templates, Projects (selected), List, Files, Documents, and Settings. The main content area is titled 'Evaluation Results' and shows a 'PASS: 1' status. The primary evaluation item is 'DMP Identifier Structure Validation', which is marked as 'PASS'. The description states: 'Validates that the DMP includes a proper Identifier and its associated type, ensuring that the maDMP is uniquely identifiable and adheres to standard structural requirements.' The timestamp is '29/05/2026, 10:46:54'. The log entry shows: 'dmp_id found: type=url, identifier=https://marek.preview.fair-wizard.com/wizard/projects/8577c04e-c768-4b19-8dcf-c6be1076306b' and 'dmp_id is valid.' The report ID is '6a19527e9d9d5244a80db5d4'. The evaluator is 'io.github.ostrails.dnpevaluatorservice.evaluators.QualityOfActions.QualityOfActionsEvaluator::dmpIdValid'. The affected element is 'dmp.dmp_id' and the completion is '100%'.

Figure 12. FAIR Wizard DMP evaluation result.

The screenshot shows the FAIR Wizard interface for an 'Example project'. The left sidebar is the same as in Figure 12. The main content area is titled 'Evaluation Results' and shows a 'FAIL: 3' status. The primary evaluation item is 'Dataset Persistent Identifier Check', which is marked as 'FAIL'. The description states: 'Checks that each dataset in the maDMP has a valid persistent identifier type (doi, handle, ark, url, other) and that the identifier is resolvable via HTTP GET. The test fails if any dataset has a missing, invalid, or unresolvable identifier.' The timestamp is '29/05/2026, 10:47:06'. The log entry shows: 'No datasets found in the maDMP.' The report ID is '6a19528a9d9d5244a80db5d6'. The evaluator is 'io.github.ostrails.dnpevaluatorservice.evaluators.completenessEvaluator.DCSCompletenessEvaluator::datasetPersistentIdentifierPresent'. The completion is '100%'. Below this, two other failed checks are visible: 'Dataset Open License Check' and 'Dataset Repository is Registered in RE3data', both marked as 'FAIL'.

Figure 13. FAIR Wizard DMP evaluation result.

5. DMP Evaluation Scenarios

The use scenarios described in this section are directly grounded in the OSTrails pilot programme defined in [D4.1 Pilots Methodology and Operational Processes](#). Across the 15 national and 8 thematic pilots, six use case topics were identified to guide pilot activities. Of these, **Topic V “co-define DMP evaluation criteria and assess DMP quality according to national policy and criteria”, is the common foundation for all three scenarios presented here.** With 5 to 6 national pilots committing to full participation, Topic V was one of the most widely adopted use cases across the pilot ecosystem, confirming community-wide demand for the evaluation infrastructure delivered in this deliverable. It directly motivated the development of the DMP Evaluation Service, and the customisation of that service to local funder and institutional needs is the central activity across all three scenarios.

The scenarios also draw on two further topics from D4.1. Topic I “develop maDMP templates to address national funders and local infrastructure”, adopted by all 15 national pilots, provides the authoring context for [UC1](#). Topic VI “extend national monitoring systems and funder reporting systems with maDMPs”, pursued by pilots focused on funder integration, informs the batch evaluation and benchmark profile capabilities demonstrated in [UC3](#).

Together, the three scenarios cover the full range of stakeholder roles and evaluation contexts that emerged consistently across the pilot ecosystem:

- **researchers** authoring DMPs within institutional platforms,
- **data stewards** reviewing DMPs for institutional approval or monitoring, and
- **funders** assessing DMP compliance at programme level.

Each scenario shares a common evaluation engine but differs in the subset of metrics invoked, the lifecycle stage assumed, and the output format consumed.

The service's alignment with the FTR vocabulary [11] ensures that results can be exchanged across platforms and consumed by downstream tools regardless of the authoring environment in which the DMP was produced.

5.1. UC1: Researcher Self-Assessment During DMP Authoring

Researchers working within DMP platforms consistently lack formative feedback during authoring, leading to incomplete or non-compliant submissions. This scenario addresses that gap directly. DMP authoring platforms such as ARGOS, DSW, DAMAP can invoke the evaluation service against a maDMP in its current state to provide inline feedback. At this stage, the evaluation is restricted to internal metrics, as the DMP is typically incomplete: datasets may have been described, but PIDs not yet assigned, and repositories named but data not yet deposited.

Figure 14. Overview of UC1: Researcher self-assessment during DMP authoring via the OSTrails DMP Evaluation Service.

The service returns a structured FTR result set indicating:

- Which completeness and quality checks pass.
- Which fail due to missing or malformed fields.
- Which are indeterminate because the relevant lifecycle stage has not yet been reached.

Results are rendered as inline annotations within the authoring interface, guiding the researcher towards filling required fields or correcting malformed values before submission. As the DMP matures and datasets are deposited, the evaluation can be extended to external feasibility metrics. In platforms such as ARGOS, where maDMP content is exposed as linked open data within the OpenAIRE Research Graph [12], the

evaluation service can cross-check declared identifiers and metadata against live graph records without requiring the researcher to re-enter information.

5.2. UC2: Data Steward Review

Data stewards at research-performing organisations lack structured tools to support DMP review, relying instead on manual checklists and subjective assessment. This scenario addresses that gap by providing a decision-support tool that can be invoked when a data steward reviews a DMP submitted by a research team for institutional approval or periodic monitoring.

Figure 15. Overview of UC2: Data steward review of submitted DMPs via the OSTrails DMP Evaluation Service.

The service applies the full metric catalogue, covering both internal and external metrics, and returns a result set that surfaces:

- Formal completeness gaps.
- Feasibility issues (e.g. a stated repository does not appear in a recognised registry).
- Compliance concerns (e.g. the declared licence does not meet funder requirements).

The aggregated benchmark score provides a summary indicator for rapid triage. The per-metric results allow the data steward to direct targeted, evidenced feedback to the relevant sections of the DMP.

5.3. UC3: Funder Compliance Assessment

Funders lack scalable tools to monitor DMP quality at programme level, relying on inconsistent manual assessment. Topic VI of D4.1 specifically targets the integration of

maDMPs into national monitoring systems and funder reporting workflows, and was identified as a priority by pilots in Norway, Austria, and Serbia. This scenario addresses both the evaluation need (Topic V) and the integration need (Topic VI) by configuring the service with a funder-specific benchmark and invoking it in batch mode against a collection of maDMPs.

Figure 16. Overview of UC3: Funder compliance assessment of maDMP collections via the OSTrails DMP Evaluation Service in batch mode.

The resulting dataset of FTR result sets enables the funder to:

- Identify systematic gaps across the cohort, such as widespread omission of embargo justifications or inconsistent use of persistent identifiers for contributors.
- Communicate targeted, evidence-based guidance to awardees.

6. Conclusion and Next steps

This deliverable documents the operational outputs of the OSTrails DMP evaluation work: **a community-developed metrics catalogue, an automated evaluation service, and integrations with major DMP authoring tools.**

Building on the framework established in D3.1 and the pilot evidence gathered in D4.2, the work described here advances the OSTrails goal of making DMP evaluation scalable, transparent, and grounded in real community needs. The co-design process engaged data stewards, tool developers, funder representatives, and domain researchers across the pilot ecosystem, generating 118 pieces of prioritised feedback that directly shaped the catalogue. Together, the metrics catalogue, the evaluation service, and the tool integrations, constitute a coherent foundation for automated, interoperable DMP assessment across European research.

The DMP Evaluation Metrics Catalogue addresses a gap that has persisted since the earliest work on maDMPs: the absence of a community-agreed, openly published set of evaluation criteria backed by executable tests. By formalising evaluation checks as linked-data metric records aligned with the RDA DMP Common Standard and serialising results using the FTR vocabulary, the catalogue and service enable machine-readable, field-level feedback that is directly actionable for researchers, data stewards, and funders. The service's plugin-based architecture further ensures that new evaluation methods can be integrated independently of the core engine, lowering the barrier for third-party adoption and extension by communities beyond OSTrails. The three use scenarios documented in [Section 5](#), grounded in the pilot use cases defined in D4.1, demonstrate how the same evaluation engine can serve different stakeholder needs across the DMP lifecycle.

Gaps and limitations identified during the co-design process are documented in [Section 3](#) and will directly inform the next iteration of the catalogue. Priority areas include, among others:

- **lifecycle cross-referencing between initial and final DMPs,**

- **controlled vocabularies for access rights and cost types,**
- **additional registry coverage, and**
- **checks for quality methods, folder structure, and data naming conventions.**

These extensions will be developed in coordination with the OSTrails pilot communities engaging with Topic V, ensuring that the next version of the catalogue continues to reflect real-world needs.

The next phase of work will focus on **extending test coverage, defining additional community and funder benchmark profiles,** and **deepening integrations with DMP authoring tools** and EOSC-aligned services. These developments will be coordinated with parallel OSTrails work on FAIR assessment metrics, ensuring that DMP evaluation and FAIRness assessment complement rather than duplicate each other. The long-term objective is to maintain the catalogue and service as living, community-governed infrastructure that evolves alongside data management practice and policy across the European research landscape.

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